

A Study on the Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Consumer Decision Making

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Abstract

With the advent in technology and increased competition among various top brands in the market the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among the retailers has become an important trend. As consumers want to make their purchasing style more simplified and easily accessible, the AI is coming to aid for such consumers. The methodology is based on secondary data collection where the data from various tech journals, articles and through keen observation on the various insights provided by the tech gurus from across the globe. With the use of AI in branding a marketer can better communicate with his customers. The marketer can maintain a good customer relationship management which allows him to retain his customers. The use of AI can lead to better understanding consumer purchasing needs and it makes the consumers more inclined towards the product or service. The study is an attempt to analyse the impact of artificial intelligence on the purchasing decisions of consumers and its effect on retailers.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Consumer Purchasing Decision, Customer Relationship Management, Buying Behaviour, Personalised Marketing.

Introduction

With the advent of technology and a dynamic environment, the rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has drastically taken over the world which has made life simpler. The influence of AI system is evident, introducing both opportunities and challenges, which has enabled the integration of future AI advances into economic and social environment. It has become evident that most people today view AI as a robotic concept but it essentially incorporates broader technology ranges that are widely used like from search engines to voice recognition, to learning/gaming structure to object detection. The development of AI has gone far and wide to make human life easier.

Artificial intelligence was formally born in a workshop conducted by IBM at Dartmouth College in 1956. Mc Carthy was the first to coin the term "Artificial Intelligence".

Artificial Intelligence is the intelligence demonstrated by machines, in contrast to the Natural Intelligence displayed by humans and other animals. The term artificial intelligence is applied when a machine mimics 'cognitive' functions that humans associate with other human minds, such as learning and problem solving. Artificial

Intelligence is a consumers best friend, unlike humans robots they are consistent as they are good at tracking and delivering high quality results which save time, money and efforts.

Artificial intelligence has recently found its way into the retail world from conversing with consumers to developing improved management strategies, AI holds a promising future for creating efficient consumer experiences and transforming management system for retail stores. The most important reason why retailers invest in AI systems is to better understand their consumer need. They also have an advantage over their competitors as they adjust their business to best fit their consumer needs.

AI can guide the customers on their journey with the brand. The self learning components of AI can continuously optimise customer satisfaction. As the marketers expand- either entering new markets or adding new products to existing markets- marketers are testing which of these technologies enable faster and less costly time to market. Not only do the marketers need to keep up with the incredible speed of product development, but need a cheaper way to access riskier markets to justify the investment of expansion into the foreign market. Added to that marketers need to learn how these technologies will provide global customers with the most personalised experience possible.

Review of Literature

- In the lines of Chris Stephenson, Chief Strategist for media agency PHD, he has cited that the rapid development in the AI space in recent years and that these developments would soon flow to consumers. A strong AI would allow computers to learn more new tasks and open up possibilities where computers can help consumers in their purchasing decisions and other practical tasks. (2016)
- As stated by John Callan the main reasons how AI will make a consumer fall for a brand are that the AIs are able to create personalization's that guides consumers, enable them to pick up where they left off and read their cues and preferences effortlessly to give them only information relevant to their needs. (2017)
- According to the study by the Forbes constant connectivity has provided consumers with an infinite amount of choices at their fingertips. 66% of UK smart phone users have thought about purchasing from brand would not have considered but now have inclined towards them because of the availability of information from the AIs.
- As per Andrew Stephens, in his article in the Forbes, he feels that the influx of affordable and accessible advanced data analytics tools, availability of increasingly rich and extensive datasets and growing acceptance among marketers of potential power make marketing decisions. AI helps cut down the decision making time for the marketers making their decisions effective and efficient.
- In the view of Quentin, Ziv and Klaus, in today's era consumers have a wide range of information and avenues to choose from. According to the economic theory, the introduction of AI should help consumers find and chose options that best suit their needs allowing them to lower their search cost, decision making cost, the unpleasant and difficult trade-offs which follows customer choice and increase the utility they derive from their choices.
- According to Mike O'Brien, AI promises to transform the future, but one thing it is doing today is letting brands use it to meet the needs and wants of the customers, to understand them better. These don't just let the retailer understand the consumers wants and needs better but also help the consumers customise their products as per their needs. It is becoming crucial for a marketer to adapt his business to smart mode because AI has become one of the many tools to delivering great customer experience.

- In the view of Christopher Gan, Visit Limsombunchai, Mike Clemes and Amy Weng, the Artificial Neural Networks are considered as a field of AI. It generally involves recognition of the problem and generalisation of problem. Recognition problems include visual applications such as learning to recognize particular words and speak them. Generalization problems include classification and prediction. Over the period, AI has been included in almost all the business helping retailers in analysing consumer choices.

Statement of Problem

The impact of Artificial Intelligence on consumer behaviour and purchasing decisions in the recent times due to advancement of technology and a dynamic environment.

Objectives

1. To know how AI influences consumers purchasing decision/ behaviour
2. To know how AI can change a retailers brand
3. To make consumers and retailers aware of the dynamic environment of brands in relation with technology

Scope of the Study

This study aids to facilitate insights on how the artificial intelligence can impact the consumer purchasing decisions. This study can act as a source of information to various retailers and consumers.

Limitations of the Study

1. Does not involve an in-depth study of AIs impact on the retailers
2. It is only consumer centric
3. Limited to consumers and brand and not concentrating on marketing

Conceptual Presentation

Artificial Intelligence helps retailer build a personalised relationship with his customer. With innovation and creativity along with machine learning, he can understand the needs and wants of the target audience and cater effectively to such demands. The introduction of AI has helped provide better assistance and information to the consumer. A lot of consumer behaviour will change if a marketer incorporates AI in his business. AI can gather more information and answer consumer queries much faster and is available to cater customer needs round the clock unlike human interference where it is time based. It can help a marketer become a monopoly in the market.

The technology is moving so fast that the consumer has more choices at the tip of his fingers and accessible at his own convenience. Earlier it was the media or agencies that controlled what the consumer wanted or what he should have, but now the consumer has control over what he wants to buy or what he wants to watch. AI has lead to customization and provides quick solutions to the problems faced by the consumers. Voice recognition is facilitating searches for various items. Consumers can consult 'robot' assistants 24/7 via messaging apps. AI based brands are increasing in number helping people make smarter choices. The expansion of AI is already helping people keep themselves updated. Automation makes everything easier for the consumer. For example, the autopilot in Tesla, chatbots for automated conversations.

The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Consumer Behaviour are as follows:

1. Consumer Perception- Virtual Personal Assistants

The popularity of AI powered Virtual Personal Assistants has boomed in recent years. Millennials are championing the Virtual Personal Assistant movement. Nearly half of this generation agree that AIs are the best technological development to date.

2. Consumer Aspirations-Robotic (Physical) Personal Assistants

A formidable number of the millennials would like an AI robotic assistant to take over at least one routine lifestyle task but the confidence interval between want and trust currently stands at 25%. Tasks that require social and emotional intelligence will remain in the human domain for the foreseeable future with only 9% of the consumers prepared to trust their clothes shopping to AI robotics.

3. Consumer Emotions- Robotic Friends & Pets

Babysitting aside a sizable proportion of Gen Z sees themselves having an AI friend in the future. Pet owners are not adverse to either. 37% of dog owners and 39% cat owners would like a furry AI companion.

4. Consumer Fears- An Artificially Intelligent Workforce

Be it in terms of AI robotics or AI software, consumers fear for their jobs in the advent of technological advancements and over half of them consider their AI replacement could happen very soon. The majority of the millennials believe that AI will replace them due to enhanced speed and accuracy and other are of the belief that their AI replacement will be due to cost savings.

5. Consumer Experience- Commercial Virtual Assistants

Consumers are more open to online AI assistance than telephone AI assistance. A marked percentage do not mind whether the customer service agent is human or machine online as long as they receive accurate and satisfying answers to their queries. As the AIs have already started taking over various brands and retail industries the speed at which its application is adopted by the consumers is remarkable and will continue to rise in the near future.

Findings

As the above spokespersons and the authors have already mentioned that Artificial Intelligence plays a very important in the day to day lives of mankind. With the advent of technology and dynamic environment it has become a necessity for retailers to upgrade themselves with the changing scenarios in order to sustain the fast growing competition and to survive in the long run.

With the use of AI in branding a marketer can better communicate with his consumers and understand their needs and wants better. The marketer can also maintain a good customer relationship management with his consumer which allows him to retain his customers.

Brand managers continuously attempt to gain advantage over a competitors and endeavour to achieve a larger market share and profit for their brand. AI has very much become a part of the consumers life. Customers are influenced largely by the innovative AI and their services which influence the consumers purchase decision.

- Virtual buying assistants, chatbots and voice activated apps are changing the way consumers interact with the brands.
- The future of marketing will look entirely different and brands are taking steps to make this vision a reality.
- The application of AI will reduce the investment made in manpower resources leading to automation which directly leads to automations.
- Brand marketers can identify key influences around the growth area as well as understanding the type of content that is resonating with the followers

- AI helps brand target the right influencers with the right content to increase awareness and diffusion.
- One of the demerit of AI is that they emotionless and need to be supervised by mankind and they are less dynamic.
- It is understood that with the application of AI in brands, has helped the consumer to save time and he can choose from variety of products and also appropriate information is available to them at the finger tips.

Suggestions

1. Although AI has been a very important aspect it has been an important reason for unemployment. The businesses should make sure that they have proportionate number of man power as well as automation.
2. All the brands should start applying AI for better consumer interactions and also for better consumer experience.
3. Without AI a business cannot function in the mere future hence marketers needs to bring in automation to help the business save time and be more effective and efficient.
4. For a business to sustain in the market it needs to be able to sell the product to its consumers and to do so he/she needs to enhance himself with technology and it also helps in consumer retention.

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